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Exploring the Impact of Cholesterol-Lowering Medications Versus Dietary Modification on Patient's Health

Ojo H.O., and Atere A.D.

Faculty of Medical Laboratory Science, Achievers University, Owo

*Corresponding Author's Email Address: happybisi@yahoo.com

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Abstract

The liver makes cholesterol, which is a vital fat necessary for hormone synthesis, maintenance of cell membrane integrity, generation of bile acids, and the synthesis of vitamin D. A particularly high LDL level needs to be taken seriously due to its huge risk of causing atherosclerosis, heart attack, and stroke, despite the preventive effects of having ideal highs of HDL cholesterol levels. Managing hypercholesterolemia remains of utmost importance to deter cardiovascular ailments, including comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension. This study examines two main strategies for lowering cholesterol: medication and dietary changes. These cholesterol-lowering drugs include statins, PCSK9 inhibitors, bile acid sequestrants, fibrates, niacin, and cholesterol absorption inhibitors that, though proved to lower LDL cholesterol levels and prevent cardiovascular events with a probability of side effects, do have compliance issues. On the other hand, good dietary changes, such as decreasing trans fats and saturated fats and increasing soluble fiber consumption with good fats, in association with dietary guidelines like DASH and the Mediterranean diet, means an economically viable and holistic way of lipid profile improvement. A comparative review of both strategies weighs the advantages and disadvantages of the two approaches while portraying the influence on treatment decisions of patient characteristics, comorbidities, the medical practitioner's advice, and the severity of hypercholesterolemia.

Keywords: Cholesterol, Dietary modification, Cardiovascular health, hypercholesterolemia, LDL cholesterol, HDL cholesterol.

1.0 Introduction

The liver produces cholesterol, a waxy, fat-like substance that is existing in every human cell and the blood. Crucial for general health, cholesterol is needed for the production of hormones, tissues, vitamin D, bile acid, the construction of cell membranes, and the facilitation of food digestion (Craig *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, eating foods produced from animals, like meat, egg yolks, and whole-milk dairy products, causes cholesterol levels to rise (National Cancer Institute, 2024).

Controlling cholesterol highly affects heart health. The higher the levels of low-density lipoprotein, the more plaques form in arteries and increase the chance for heart disease and stroke. The greatest way cholesterol can bring down the risk of stroke and heart attacks is by working towards the increase of high-density lipoprotein and the decrease of the low-density lipoprotein (Das and Ingole, 2023).

Controlling cholesterol can also improve cardiovascular health by lowering the risk of coming up with heart-related conditions such as peripheral artery disease, angina, and heart attacks (World Health Organization, 2024).

In addition, beyond heart disease, high cholesterol levels fall under conditions such as diabetes and hypertension. Proper bad cholesterol control decreases the risk of contracting other health concerns. It also promotes better health among people through good eating and exercise habits (Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care, 2022).

2.0 An Overview of Diet Changes and Medications that Decrease Cholesterol

Medication aimed at lowering cholesterol is therefore used in the treatment of cardiovascular disease. Various mechanisms are employed by this treatment. These medications lower the chances of heart attack and stroke; hence, their use among individuals suffering from high cholesterol levels is of utmost importance. Examples of cholesterol-lowering medications include PCSK9, bile acid sequestrants, and statins (Feingold, 2024).

Blood cholesterol levels can be fundamentally regulated through dietary adjustment, and heart-healthy eating can dramatically reduce the chance of heart disease. The major objective of dietary changes for lowering blood cholesterol is to increase intake of foods high in soluble fiber and unsaturated fats while cutting back on trans and saturated fat intake (Ghodeswar *et al.*, 2023).

3.0 Choosing Healthy Fats

When taken correctly, unsaturated fats of the polyunsaturated and monounsaturated varieties, can help reduce LDL cholesterol. Monounsaturated fats are found in almonds, seeds, avocados, and olive oil. Polyunsaturated fats are found in walnuts, soybean oil, flaxseeds, and Fatty fish like trout, salmon, and mackerel (Harvard Medical School, 2021).

3.1.1 Reducing Saturated and Trans Fats

There are ways in which dietary modifications will essentially affect the cholesterol level in the blood, and heart-healthy eating will considerably reduce the chances of having cardiovascular diseases. Dietary modifications to reduce blood cholesterol mainly work toward reducing the intake of trans and saturated fats while increasing the intake of soluble fiber and foods rich in unsaturated fats (Lichtenstein, 2014).

3.1.2 Increasing Soluble Fiber Intake

Soluble fiber attaches itself to cholesterol in the digestive tract, stopping it from being absorbed into the bloodstream and then encouraging its removal out of the body. The foods containing soluble fiber consist of barley, oats, legumes like beans, lentils, and peas; fruits like berries, oranges, and apples; and vegetables such as Brussels sprouts and carrots (Soliman, 2019).

3.1.3 Incorporating Plant Sterols and Stanols

Natural substances called plant sterols and stanols can be discovered in trace levels in whole grains, nuts, seeds, and fruits as well as vegetables. Higher doses obtained from fortified foods or supplements may aid in preventing the intestines from absorbing cholesterol, lowering LDL cholesterol levels (Trautwein *et al.*, 2018).

3.1.4 Emphasizing Whole Foods

There should be an emphasis on plant-based lipids, lean proteins, whole grains, and fruits in any strategy for lowering cholesterol. These foods are usually abundant in fiber, antioxidants, and minerals that generally promote cardiovascular health and also help keep cholesterol levels within the normal ranges (Penn Medicine, 2019).

3.1.5 Limiting Dietary Cholesterol:

Despite being strong dietary cholesterol sources, eggs, seafood, and organ meats have less of an impact on levels of blood cholesterol than trans and saturated fats. Individuals who have heart disease or high cholesterol should especially avoid consuming these foods in excess (Carson *et al.*, 2020; Michael Merschel, 2023).

3.1.6 Tracking Caloric Intake and Portion Sizes

Any excess of calories consumed, no matter where they come from, can cause dyslipidemia and weight gain. Keeping lipid profiles optimal and maintaining a healthy weight necessitate controlling portion sizes and finding equilibrium between energy intake and expenditure (Plachta-Danielzik *et al.*, 2008; Romieu *et al.*, 2017).

4.0 Importance of Understanding the Impact on the Patient's Health

An increase in cholesterol corresponds to an increased cardiovascular illnesses, such as heart attacks and strokes. Consequently, to prevent these potentially lethal problems, medical experts monitor and assess cholesterol levels (Plachta-Danielzik *et al.*, 2008). Medical professionals keep an eye on and assess cholesterol levels to prevent these potentially deadly illnesses.

5.0 Cholesterol-Lowering Medications

Types of cholesterol-lowering medications are Statins, PCSK9 inhibitors, Bile acids sequestrants, Fibrates, Niacin, Omega-3, Cholesterol absorption inhibitors

5.1 Mechanism of Action of Cholesterol-Lowering Medications

5.1.1 Mechanism of Action of Statins

Statins can reduce the biosynthesis of cholesterol mostly in the liver, where they are preferentially distributed. They can also modify lipid metabolism by inhibiting HMG-CoA reductase. A favorable relationship exists between the percentage drop in LDL cholesterol and the antiatherosclerotic effects of statins. Apart from their hypolipidemic activity, they can also have antiatherosclerotic properties. Because mevalonate metabolism produces a number of isoprenoids that are necessary for a number of biological functions, such as cholesterol synthesis and the control of the cell proliferation and differentiation, inhibiting HMG-CoA reductase has positive pleiotropic effects (Stancu and Sima, 2001). As a result, statins are the most effective hypolipidemic medications that have decreased the death rate in coronary patients, greatly lowering the incidence of coronary activities in primary and secondary prevention (Control and (US), 2003).

Figure 1: Diagram for the mechanism of action of statin (Sainz and Serra, 2023)

5.1.2 Mechanism of Action of Inhibitors of PCSK9.

PCSK9 inhibitors work by blocking PCSK9's function with monoclonal antibodies, which decreases LDL receptor degradation and raises LDL cholesterol clearance.

PCSK9 is a proprotein convertase that helps the liver's breakdown of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) receptors. Familial hypercholesterolemia is experienced in patients as a result of a mutation in the PCSK9 gene, thereby causing a reduction in the quantity of LDL receptors on hepatocyte surfaces with a decreased ability for plasma clearance of LDL cholesterol (Page and Watts, 2016).

Figure 2: Mechanism of action of PCSK9 Inhibitors (Page and Watts, 2016).

6.0 Efficacy and Effectiveness of Cholesterol-Lowering Medication

Numerous research has demonstrated the efficiency of cholesterol-lowering drugs, such as statins, in lowering cholesterol levels, especially LDL (bad) cholesterol. At the prevention settings, both at the primary and secondary level, they have proved to reduce the cardiovascular events' risk, such as heart attacks and strokes. On average, fluvastatin (40 mg), pravastatin (34%), lovastatin and simvastatin (37%), atorvastatin (49%), and rosuvastatin (53%) decreased LDL cholesterol (Feingold, 2024).

However, a number of variables, including the patient's baseline risk factors and treatment compliance, can affect how effective they are (Goldenberg and Glueck, 2009).

7.0 Side Effects and Risks

Common adverse effects of cholesterol lowering drugs include gastrointestinal disturbances such as diarrhea, constipation, nausea, or vomiting. Some patients may also experience muscle aches, liver enzyme abnormalities, sleep disturbances depending on the class of drug used.

8.0 Dietary Modification

8.1 Dietary Guidelines for Cholesterol Management: The guidelines include

8.1.1 A low-fat diet

Saturated as well as trans fats, which are present in many processed foods and animal products, are the main targets of a low-fat diet (Spajić, 2020) Rather, it stresses the consumption of good fats from foods such as fatty fish, avocados, almonds, and seeds. When paired with other healthy lifestyle choices like consistent exercise and keeping a healthy weight, cholesterol and heart disease risk are decreased. Not

all fats are unhealthy, Some are actually excellent and consulting with a qualified dietitian or medical professional may result in tailored advice based unique needs Sand health goals (Liu *et al.*, 2017).

8.1.2 Plant-based Diet

Plant-based foods such fruits, legumes, nuts, seeds, whole grains, and vegetables make up the majority of a diet that is rich in plant-based foods and low in animal products (Kent *et al.*, 2022). This dietary pattern has been associated with several health benefits, including improved weight control, lowered cholesterol, a lower risk of heart disease, and improved overall health. When carefully designed, plant-based diets can still include all the necessary nutrients while being customized to meet dietary requirements and personal tastes. A variety of plant-based foods must be consumed in order to provide adequate intake of vitamins, minerals, and other nutrients (McManus, 2024).

The Mediterranean diet, which is followed by nations that border the Mediterranean Sea, was modeled after ancient dietary customs. Usually, it entails eating whole grains, legumes, nuts, seeds, fruits, and vegetables in large quantities. Fat primarily comes from olive oil, with small amounts of fish, poultry as well as dairy goods like yogurt and cheese. The Mediterranean diet has many well-known health benefits, including lowering cholesterol, lowering the chance of heart disease, enhancing mental clarity, and lengthening life (Guasch-Ferré and Willett, 2021).

This dietary pattern's high fiber, healthy fat, and antioxidant content are believed to have a part in its beneficial benefits on general health. It is crucial to remember that the Mediterranean diet is more than simply certain foods; it is a way of eating and living that includes regular exercise, social interaction, and enjoying meals. This diet can help you maintain your health and well-being in a tasty and long-lasting way (Healthline, 2023).

8.1.3 Dash Diet

A diet plan called the DASH (Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension) diet aims to prevent and manage hypertension, or high blood pressure. It places an emphasis on eating foods high in fiber, potassium, calcium, magnesium, and other nutrients while ingesting less salt (Healthline, 2023).

Important elements of the DASH diet consist of:

1. Fruits and vegetables: Highlighting a variety of fruits and vegetables rich in vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants.
2. Whole grains: go for quinoa, brown rice, and whole wheat bread, oats, and other nutrient-dense, high-fiber whole grains.
3. Lean proteins: consuming more lean protein sources, such as fish, poultry, lentils, beans, and a decrease in processed and red meats.
4. Low-fat dairy: eating dairy products like cheese, yogurt, and milk that are low in fat or have none at all since they include calcium.
5. Nuts, seeds, and legumes: because of their rich levels of protein, fiber, and good fat., eat these items in moderation.
6. Limiting sodium: lowering salt consumption by staying away from packaged and processed foods, using herbs and spices rather than salt to season food, and choosing low-sodium options when they are offered.

It has been demonstrated that adhering to the DASH diet lowers blood pressure and the risk of heart disease, stroke, and other illnesses (Dring *et al.*, 2022). To customize the DASH diet to unique requirements and health objectives, qualified nutritionists or medical specialists should be consulted

9.0 Impact of Dietary Changes on Cholesterol Level

Eating fewer foods high in saturated fat and staying away from foods high in trans-fat to lower cholesterol because bad cholesterol (LDL) is elevated by these lipids (Spajić, 2020) Also, nutrients needed for a healthy, active life by increasing intake of soluble fiber and plant-based foods can lower LDL cholesterol.

10.0 Role of Exercise in Conjunction with Dietary Modifications

Regular exercise can help to combat high cholesterol. A person can reduce their total and LDL cholesterol levels by exercising via walking, jogging, cycling, and swimming. It is common for an individual's HDL cholesterol levels to rise. by these exercises as well (Barone Gibbs *et al.*, 2021) Approximately 150 minutes of moderately intense aerobic activity each week can improve heart health overall, according to studies.

11.0 Comparative Analysis

11.1 Merits and Demerits of Cholesterol-Lowering Medications

Cholesterol-lowering medications, such as statins, have both merits and demerits:

11.1.1 Merits

1. Effectiveness: Cardiovascular disease risk can be decreased by using cholesterol-lowering drugs, which are very successful at lowering LDL (bad) cholesterol levels.
2. Widely Available: These pharmaceuticals are commonly accessible and prescribed by medical professionals. to manage cholesterol levels.
3. Research-backed: Large-scale clinical trials have demonstrated its efficacy after much research.
4. Preventive Benefits: They can aid in preventing cardiovascular diseases including heart attacks and strokes. events, especially in people with high risk factors or heart disease.
5. Well-Tolerated: These drugs often have few adverse effects and are well-tolerated by a large number of people.

11.1.2 Demerits

1. Side Effects: Some people may experience negative side effects, such as stomach issues, liver problems, or muscle soreness, when taking cholesterol-lowering medications.
2. Dependency: Using drugs can lead to a feeling of dependence and deter some people from changing their lifestyles as they should.
3. Cost: Drugs that decrease cholesterol can be expensive, especially for those without insurance.
4. Long-term Use: Although research in this area is still underway, long-term use of these drugs may raise concerns about possible effects on other body systems or organs.
5. Compliance: Some patients can have trouble adhering to their prescribed regimens, which could lead to less than optimal cholesterol control.

Dietary modifications also have their own set of pros and cons:

11.1.3 Pros

1. Natural Approach: Dietary changes that emphasize natural foods and nutrients can offer numerous health benefits. beyond merely reducing cholesterol.
2. Holistic Health: A nutritious diet can improve general health by lowering the risk of heart disease, diabetes, and some forms of cancer, among other chronic illnesses.
3. Sustainable: Unlike prescription drugs, dietary modifications can become long-lasting lifestyle habits.
4. Empowerment: By altering their diet, people may take control of their health and wellbeing.
5. Cost-effective: Changing to a healthy diet can often be less expensive than depending just on medicine.

11.1.4 Cons

1. **Demands Discipline:** It could be challenging for some people to alter their eating patterns, particularly if they are accustomed to particular eating patterns.
2. **Time-consuming:** Healthy meal planning and preparation can take a lot of time, especially for those who lead busy lives.
3. **Individual Variability:** It might be challenging to identify a one-size-fits-all strategy because dietary recommendations may differ based on personal factors like age, gender, health state, and cultural preferences.
4. **Social Impact:** It may be challenging to follow dietary restrictions in social situations, such as when dining out or attending activities, which could lead to social discomfort.
5. **Possible Nutrient shortages:** If certain vital nutrients are not sufficiently replenished or supplemented, drastically changing dietary habits without the right advice may result in nutrient shortages.

12.0 Factors Influencing Treatment of Choice

The following factors affect how hypercholesterolemia is treated:

Features and preferences of patients

Hypercholesterolemia severity

Medical disorders that coexist

Factors related to lifestyle

Guidelines and recommendations from physicians

12.1.1 Patients' Characteristics and Preferences

Treatment of hypercholesterolemia is significantly influenced by the traits and preferences of the patient. Treatment choices may be influenced by variables like age, gender, lifestyle, comorbidities, and individual preferences. For instance, older patients might place a higher priority on limiting side effects, whereas younger patients would favor more aggressive treatment alternatives. Furthermore, patients who have already experienced statin resistance could choose different drugs or changes to their lifestyle (Strandberg *et al.*, 2014).

12.1.2 Severity of Hypercholesterolemia

One important consideration while choosing a treatment is the degree of hypercholesterolemia. Dietary and exercise modifications may be adequate for moderate instances (Enkhmaa *et al.*, 2018). However, medicine, such as statins, is frequently advised for moderate to severe instances or individuals who are at high risk of cardiovascular events. The patient's lipid profile, general cardiovascular risk, comorbidities, and possible drug side effects are typically taken into consideration when deciding which drugs to prescribe and how severe the course of therapy should be (Rossini *et al.*, 2022).

12.1.3 Coexisting Medical Conditions

Coexisting medical disorders play a significant influence in choosing the best course of treatment for hypercholesterolemia. Treatment regimens may need to be modified or pharmaceutical choices may be influenced by certain medical problems. For instance, people with diabetes or hypertension might benefit from drugs like combination treatments or specific kinds of statins that have cardiovascular advantages beyond decreasing cholesterol (Martinez-Hervas and Ascaso, 2023). Likewise, people who have renal or liver issues could require other medications or frequent monitoring to effectively control

hypercholesterolemia while avoiding possible side effects. By considering concurrent medical conditions, healthcare providers can create treatment programs that are tailored to the patient's needs and address hypercholesterolemia and general health (Lan *et al.*, 2023).

12.1.4 Lifestyle Factors

Lifestyle factors are crucial in the management of hypercholesterolemia and are often used in conjunction with or as a foundation for medication. Changing to a diet high in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and lean proteins that is heart-healthy while cutting back on saturated and trans fats will help lower cholesterol levels. Because it can enhance cardiovascular health and cholesterol profiles, regular exercise is also crucial (Kirkpatrick *et al.*, 2023)

Additional lifestyle choices include controlling one's weight, quitting smoking, and reducing alcohol consumption. In minor cases of hypercholesterolemia, lifestyle modifications may be enough for some people, and in more severe situations, they may be used as an adjuvant therapy in conjunction with medication. As part of an all-encompassing strategy to manage hypercholesterolemia, healthcare professionals frequently stress lifestyle changes with the goal of lowering overall cardiovascular risk and increasing the efficacy of medication (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025).

12.1.5 Physician Recommendations and Guidelines

Choosing the best course of treatment for hypercholesterolemia depends heavily on physician advice and recommendations. advising medical professionals on the best, most scientifically supported methods for controlling elevated cholesterol. They take into account things like cardiovascular disease risk factors, possible drug adverse effects, and the patient's general health. Patients can receive the finest care possible, customized to meet their specific needs, by adhering to these recommendations (Grundy and Feingold, 2025).

13.0 Laboratory Diagnosis

The laboratory diagnosis of hypercholesterolemia involves measurements of blood triglycerides, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol. Increased cardiovascular risk and hypercholesterolemia are frequently linked to increased LDL and total cholesterol levels. Furthermore, increased triglycerides and low HDL cholesterol may also play a role in the diagnosis. These metrics offer useful data for determining cardiovascular risk and directing therapeutic choices (Lee and Siddiqui, 2023).

Figure 3: Cholesterol level chart

Adopted from(McDougall, 2025)

14.0 Recommendation

1. lowering low-density lipoprotein (LDL) by eating a diet that is heart-healthy.
2. Exercise frequently to lower LDL.
3. Frequent monitoring of cholesterol levels.
4. Deal with lifestyle elements such as stress and smoking.
5. If necessary, take medication.

15.0 Conclusion

The body uses cholesterol extensively, but it is crucial to control cholesterol levels, particularly those of low-density lipoprotein, to keep the heart healthy overall and avoid various secondary health problems. Although there are several variables that influence the therapeutic choice, lowering blood cholesterol is the main goal.

References

1. Barone Gibbs, B., Hivert, M.-F., Jerome, G. J., Kraus, W. E., Rosenkranz, S. K., Schorr, E. N., Spartano, N. L., & Lobelo, F. (2021). Physical activity as a critical component of first-line treatment for elevated blood pressure or cholesterol: Who, what, and how? A scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Hypertension*, 78(2), e26–e37. <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYP.000000000000196>
2. Carson, J. A. S., Lichtenstein, A. H., Anderson, C. A. M., Appel, L. J., Kris-Etherton, P. M., Meyer, K. A., Petersen, K., Polonsky, T., & Van Horn, L. (2020). Dietary cholesterol and cardiovascular risk: A science advisory from the American Heart Association. *Circulation*, 141(3), e39–e53. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0000000000000743>
3. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2025, February 13). Preventing high cholesterol. <https://www.cdc.gov/cholesterol/prevention/index.html>
4. Chukwura, J., Fay, M. M., & Labarthe, D. (2003). A public health action plan to prevent heart disease and stroke. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
5. Craig, M., Yarrarapu, S. N. S., & Dimri, M. (2023). Biochemistry, cholesterol. In StatPearls [Internet]. StatPearls Publishing. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK513326/>
6. Das, P., & Ingole, N. (2023). Lipoproteins and their effects on the cardiovascular system. *Cureus*, 15(11).
7. Dring, J. C., Forma, A., Chilimoniuk, Z., Dobosz, M., Teresiński, G., Buszewicz, G., Flieger, J., Cywka, T., Januszewski, J., & Baj, J. (2022). Essentiality of trace elements in pregnancy, fertility, and gynecologic cancers—A state-of-the-art review. *Nutrients*, 14(1), Article 185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14010185>
8. Enkhmaa, B., Surampudi, P., Anuurad, E., & Berglund, L. (2018, September 11). Lifestyle changes: Effect of diet, exercise, functional food, and obesity treatment on lipids and lipoproteins. In Endotext. MDText.com, Inc. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK326737/>
9. Feingold, K. R. (2024, February 12). Cholesterol lowering drugs. In Endotext. MDText.com, Inc. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK395573/>
10. Ghodeswar, G. K., Dube, A., & Khobragade, D. (2023). Impact of lifestyle modifications on cardiovascular health: A narrative review. *Cureus*, 15(7). <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.42616>
11. Goldenberg, N., & Glueck, C. (2009). Efficacy, effectiveness and real life goal attainment of statins in managing cardiovascular risk. *Vascular Health and Risk Management*, 5, 369.
12. Grundy, S. M., & Feingold, K. R. (2025). Guidelines for the management of high blood cholesterol. In Endotext. MDText.com, Inc. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK305897/>
13. Guasch-Ferré, M., & Willett, W. C. (2021). The Mediterranean diet and health: A comprehensive overview. *Journal of Internal Medicine*, 290(3), 549–566.
14. Harvard Medical School. (2021). Know the facts about fats. Harvard Health Publishing. <https://www.health.harvard.edu/staying-healthy/know-the-facts-about-fats>
15. Healthline. (2023). Mediterranean diet 101: Meal plan, foods list, and tips. <https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/mediterranean-diet-meal-plan-how-to-follow-it>
16. Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care. (2022). Overview: High cholesterol. In InformedHealth.org. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK279318/>
17. Kent, G., Kehoe, L., Flynn, A., & Walton, J. (2022). Plant-based diets: A review of the definitions and nutritional role in the adult diet. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 81(1), 62–74.
18. Kirkpatrick, C. F., Sikand, G., Petersen, K. S., Anderson, C. A. M., Aspary, K. E., Bolick, J. P., Kris-Etherton, P. M., & Maki, K. C. (2023). Nutrition interventions for adults with dyslipidemia: A clinical perspective from the National Lipid Association. *Journal of Clinical Lipidology*, 17(4), 428–451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacl.2023.05.003>
19. Lan, N. S. R., Bajaj, A., Watts, G. F., & Cuchel, M. (2023). Recent advances in the management and implementation of care for familial hypercholesterolaemia. *Pharmacological Research*, 194, 106857. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2023.106857>

20. Lee, Y., & Siddiqui, W. J. (2023). Cholesterol levels. In StatPearls [Internet]. StatPearls Publishing. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK542294/>
21. Lichtenstein, A. H. (2014). Dietary trans fatty acids and cardiovascular disease risk: Past and present. *Current Atherosclerosis Reports*, 16(8), Article 433.
22. Liu, A. G., Ford, N. A., Hu, F. B., Zelman, K. M., Mozaffarian, D., & Kris-Etherton, P. M. (2017). A healthy approach to dietary fats: Understanding the science and taking action to reduce consumer confusion. *Nutrition Journal*, 16(1), Article 53.
23. McDougall, J. (2025, March 24). Common health problems: High cholesterol. Dr. McDougall's Health & Medical Center. <https://www.drmcDougall.com/education/common-health-problems/high-cholesterol/>
24. McManus, K. D. (2024). What is a plant-based diet and why should you try it? Harvard Health Publishing. <https://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/what-is-a-plant-based-diet-and-why-should-you-try-it-2018092614760>
25. Merschel, M. (2023, August 25). Here's the latest on dietary cholesterol and how it fits in with a healthy diet. American Heart Association. <https://www.heart.org/en/news/2023/08/25/heres-the-latest-on-dietary-cholesterol-and-how-it-fits-in-with-a-healthy-diet>
26. Martinez-Hervas, S., & Ascaso, J. F. (2023). Hypercholesterolemia. In *Encyclopedia of endocrine diseases* (pp. 320–326). Elsevier.
27. Page, M. M., & Watts, G. F. (2016). PCSK9 inhibitors – Mechanisms of action. *Australian Prescriber*, 39(5), 164–167.
28. Penn Medicine. (2019, September). The benefits of eating a whole foods, plant-based diet. Chester County Hospital Health e-Living. <https://www.chestercountyhospital.org/news/health-eliving-blog/2019/september/the-benefits-of-eating-a-whole-foods-plant-based-diet>
29. Plachta-Danielzik, S., Landsberg, B., Bosy-Westphal, A., Johannsen, M., Lange, D., & Müller, M. J. (2008). Energy gain and energy gap in normal-weight children: Longitudinal data of the KOPS. *Obesity*, 16(4), 777–783.
30. Romieu, I., Dossus, L., Barquera, S., Blotière, H. M., Franks, P. W., Gunter, M., Hwalla, N., Hursting, S. D., Leitzmann, M., Margetts, B., Nishida, C., Potischman, N., Seidell, J., Stepien, M., Wang, Y., Westerterp, K., Winichagoon, P., Wiseman, M., & Willett, W. C. (2017). Energy balance and obesity: What are the main drivers? *Cancer Causes & Control*, 28(3), 247–258.
31. Rossini, E., Biscetti, F., Rando, M. M., Nardella, E., Cecchini, A. L., Nicolazzi, M. A., Covino, M., Gasbarrini, A., Massetti, M., & Flex, A. (2022). Statins in high cardiovascular risk patients: Do comorbidities and characteristics matter? *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(16), 9326.
32. Sainz, J., & Serra, M. (2023). Influence of pharmacogenetics on the diversity of response to statins associated with adverse drug reactions. *Advances in Laboratory Medicine / Avances en Medicina de Laboratorio*, 4, 1–10.
33. Soliman, G. A. (2019). Dietary fiber, atherosclerosis, and cardiovascular disease. *Nutrients*, 11(5), 1155.
34. Spajić, D. G. (2020). Strategies to achieve a healthy diet and health: Reduction of trans fat and saturated fatty acids. In F. J. Barba, P. Putnik, & D. B. Kovačević (Eds.), *Agri-food industry strategies for healthy diets and sustainability* (pp. 103–121). Academic Press.
35. Staels, B., Dallongeville, J., Auwerx, J., Schoonjans, K., Leitersdorf, E., & Fruchart, J.-C. (1998). Mechanism of action of fibrates on lipid and lipoprotein metabolism. *Circulation*, 98(19), 2088–2093.
36. Stancu, C., & Sima, A. (2001). Statins: Mechanism of action and effects. *Journal of Cellular and Molecular Medicine*, 5(4), 378–387.
37. Strandberg, T., Kolehmainen, L., & Vuorio, A. (2014). Evaluation and treatment of older patients with hypercholesterolemia: A clinical review. *JAMA*, 312(11), 1136–1144. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2014.10924>

38. Trautwein, E. A., Vermeer, M. A., Hiemstra, H., & Ras, R. T. (2018). LDL-cholesterol lowering of plant sterols and stanols—Which factors influence their efficacy? *Nutrients*, 10(9), 1262.
39. World Health Organization. (2024, April 26). Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))